

Middle East University
Faculty of Business Administration

LEGAL COMPANIES VS. ILLEGAL AND FRANCHISES IN LEBANON:
THE CHALLENGES TO MANAGE A BUSINESS IN A LOW
MARKET SHARE COUNTRY

A Thesis

Presented in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements for the Degree
Master of Business Administration

by

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THESIS ABSTRACT

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Title: LEGAL COMPANIES VS. ILLEGAL AND FRANCHISES IN LEBANON:
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SHARE COUNTRY

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Though Lebanese SMEs should be thriving, many are facing external and internal challenges. Externally, though the Lebanese government is supposed to regulate the business market share, many family businesses are operating illegally, seeking to reduce costs, therefore causing unfair competition. In addition, legal businesses face strong competition from franchise companies. Internally, Lebanese businesses use favoritism to recruit and managers aim to satisfy the owner more than achieving the objectives of the business, resulting in both low job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Through a mixed-method methodology to analyze the perspectives of 86 participants, this study sheds light on 1) the reasons why Lebanese SMEs decide to operate legally, illegally, or as a franchise, 2) the owners' behavior regarding finances and human resources management, 3) the relationships between owners and employees, 4) the profitability impact of illegal and franchises on legal SMEs, and 5) the future of SMEs in Lebanon. The study ends with theoretical and

practical implications for SMEs, the government, as well as recommendations for future research.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

LIST OF FIGURES	vi
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	vii
1. INTRODUCTION.....	1
Background.....	1
Problem Statement.....	2
Research Questions.....	3
2. LITERATURE REVIEW	4
Small and Medium Enterprises.....	4
SMEs in Lebanon	6
Reasons for Operating Legally, Illegally, or as a Franchise.....	8
Reasons for Operating Legally	8
Reasons for Operating Illegally	11
Reasons for Operating as a Franchise	11
Owners' Behavior Regarding Finances and Human Resources	12
Finances	12
Human Resources	13
Relationships Between Owners and Employees.....	14
Profitability Impact: Illegal and Franchise	15
Future of SMEs in Lebanon.....	15
3. METHODOLOGY	17
Research Design	17
Data Collection Methods	17
Data Analysis Methods.....	18
Ethical Considerations	19
4. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS	20
Population and Sample	20
Reasons for Operating Illegally, Legally or as a Franchise.....	22
Survey Analysis.....	22
Interview Analysis.....	24
Owner's Behavior Regarding Financing and Human Resources Functions	26
Survey Analysis.....	26
Interview Analysis.....	35
Relationship Between Owners and Employees	38
Survey Analysis.....	38

Profitability Impact: Illegal and Franchise	39
Survey Analysis.....	39
Interviews Analysis	41
Future of SMEs in Lebanon.....	42
Survey Analysis.....	42
Interviews Analysis	44
5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS.....	48
Conclusion	48
Implications	49
Theoretical Implications.....	50
Governmental Implications	51
Implications for SMEs.....	52
REFERENCES	54
APPENDIXES	57
A. INTERVIEW GUIDE.....	57
B. SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE	59

LIST OF FIGURES

1. Age Groups	22
2. Reason for not registering.....	23
3. Reasons for selecting a legal form of business	24
4. Organizational form.....	27
5. Role in the firm	28
6. Number of family members who are investors.....	28
7. Financing sources.....	29
8. Family members who are full-time employees.....	30
9. Family members who are part-time employees	30
10. Conducting training decrease problems of transition	31
11. Type of managers.....	32
12. Effective management involves meetings	33
13. Management conflict affect the growth of local business	33
14. Lack of management diversity affects the growth of local business	34
15. Relationships between owners and employees	39
16. Problems faced by SMEs	40
17. Succession plans and effective management	43
18. Long-term plans lead to the success of the business.....	44

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Background

When students graduate, they dream of owning their business, thus becoming their own boss (Amubode, Rauf-Lawal, & Owodiong-Idemeko, 2016). The variety of innovative businesses are growing because of the increasing of number of graduated students who are qualified and creative, resulting in an increase in the establishment of small businesses. While some of them are established legally, others are not registered. This situation is occurring in Lebanon and in many countries where the government is not strict in regulating the establishment of businesses. To add to the competitive challenges faced by small and medium-size enterprises (SME) in a small market as the Lebanese market, there is an increased operation of global franchise firms.

In the last decade, the Lebanese government, public and private sectors launched programs to support the Lebanese SMEs by enhancing the quality standards focusing on excessive trainings and professional workshops (Khoury, 2014). Furthermore, “MoET launched the Internationalization Support initiative to subsidize participation of Lebanese firms in global fairs” (Khoury, 2014, p.15). Moreover, it reduced the unemployment rate in the Lebanese youth, by establishing financing plans, encouraging creativity and technology awareness, developing programs to train and coach the workforce. SMEs play an essential role in improving the Lebanese economic dynamism and creating more job vacancies (Khoury, 2013). Furthermore,

as a result of SMEs success, some of them have been substantially developed to become international corporations (Farris & Moore, 2004). Three factors are considered crucial for SMEs successful stories: financial facilities, management efficiency, and quality decision making (Hughes, 2008).

Problem Statement

Though Lebanese SMEs should be thriving, many are facing external and internal challenges. Externally, though the Lebanese government is supposed to regulate the business market share, many family businesses are operating illegally seeking to reduce costs, therefore causing unfair competition. In addition, legal businesses face strong competition from franchise companies. Internally, Lebanese businesses use favoritism to recruit and managers aim to satisfy the owner more than achieving the objectives of the business, resulting in both low job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to analyze the ethical, competition, and management challenges faced by entrepreneurs and their effects on the profitability of SMEs in Lebanon.

The importance of this study lays in that it covers different issues and problems faced by legal small businesses in Lebanon, such as unfair competition from illegal businesses from one side, and strong franchises from the other side. This study will provide Lebanese entrepreneurs, specifically small family businesses, a clear picture of their challenges and opportunities, and recommendations to succeed in a small market share country.

Research Questions

1. Why do small family businesses decide to operate illegally, legally or as a franchise in Lebanon?
2. How do owners of SMEs behave regarding financing and human resources functions in Lebanon?
3. What is the nature of the relationship between employees and the owners of SMEs?
4. What is the impact of franchise and illegal business on the profitability of local legal businesses in Lebanon?
5. What is the future of legal, illegal, and franchise businesses in the small Lebanese market?

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

The review of the literature is organized in the five research questions, preceded by a description of SMEs.

Small and Medium Enterprises

SMEs are companies characterized by less than 40 employees according to Kafalat (Abi Habib, 2008). SMEs are the dynamic wheel of an emerging economy that add value, increase competitive advantage, and support economic development (Pissarides, 1999).

SMEs face various obstacles embedded in the economic, legal, and administrative environment of the economy. These obstacles stem from legal restrictions, limited expertise, unfavorable infrastructure conditions and access to credit difficulties. There is generally accepted belief that limited financing—e. g. limited access to working capital and long-term credit—is the major obstacle to the growth of SMEs (Pissarides, 1999). The major obstacle facing SMEs is their inability to obtain funds from the formal financial systems (Eikebrokk & Olsen, 2005). Therefore, there is a need to find alternative solutions that would help SMEs access financing, grow, and thus fulfill their widely accepted role as a driver of socio economic welfare.

Financing allows acquiring assets, creating employment, running operations, developing market strategies, and channels of distribution. Funding needs vary

according to the life cycle of the business being the least in the first stage of concept development and the second stage of amassing resources, and then rising in the stage of product development to reach its highest in business development (Stratos & Panos, 2002).

The financing problem of SMEs is not a new issue and has been resurfacing since the 1980s. A typical example is that of 1931, when the British Committee on Finance and Industry found that SMEs have more difficulty in attaining capital in comparison to bigger firms (Eikebrokk & Olsen, 2005). This concept was supported by a study done by the US Department of Commerce during the period of 1935 through 1940 that also found that SMEs face difficulties obtaining funds (Buzzell, Gale, & Sultan, 1975). Therefore, SMEs need an improved information flow via increased awareness of financing assistance available, to enhance the projection of their cash flows (Michael, 2002).

Information asymmetry is an obstacle to financing. Banks and creditors face difficulties in collecting or receiving information from borrowers. The information is usually obscure and makes risk assessment a hassle to lenders (Vishwanath, 2007). Asymmetric information can occur prior to and after financing. The question of credibility of information at this stage is essential. The financier can hope that the money will be paid back on time. A type of information asymmetry arises when companies change their actions after receiving credit. They might change their strategies and objectives, their managerial hierarchy, and even increase risky investments.

The family nature of many SMEs provides them with family equity financing opportunities. However, family association poses issues of conflict and sustainability (Neubauer & Lank, 1998). Family can interfere in ownership without managing the

business or with controlling all the management issues. In both types of interferences, families desire to maintain control in the firm, hence limiting equity financing from outside of the family (Zhenyu, 2007).

SMEs in Lebanon

“Lebanon has many investment enabling strengths that have encouraged foreign companies to set up offices in recent years. Lebanon’s key advantages include a free market economy, the absence of controls on the movement of capital and foreign exchange, a highly educated labor force, good quality of life, and limited restrictions on investors” (U.S. Department of State, 2013, para. 2).

In Lebanon, it is difficult to assess the contribution of SMEs to the economy. There is a severe shortage of information and data concerning the subject. With SMEs dominating the Lebanese economy (Census of Buildings and Establishments, 1996), it is important to assess the overall environment and underline what is being done in order to enhance their productivity and encourage investments. SMEs are in Mount Lebanon (55%) and Beirut (23%), and operate mostly in trading (53%), real estate (13%) and manufacturing (12%) (El Khoury, 2013).

“Kafalat is a Lebanese financial company with a public concern that assists SMEs to access commercial bank funding. Kafalat helps SMEs by providing loan guarantees based on business plans and feasibility studies that show the viability of the proposed business activity. It processes guarantee applications for loans that are to be provided by Lebanese banks to SMEs operating throughout Lebanon” (Banque du Liban, 2017, p. 1).

Thus, by the help of a loan, many new graduated entrepreneurs convert their written business ideas to successful, efficient, and profitable businesses.

“Kafalat guaranteed loans benefit from interest rate subsidies. These subsidies have been set up to mitigate the crowding out effect of the high interest rates in Lebanon that are induced by public sector borrowing. The interest rate subsidies are financed by the Lebanese treasury and administered by the Central Bank of Lebanon” (Kafalat Basic, 2011, p. 2).

Several Lebanese governmental bodies are working on helping local SMEs. The Ministry of Economy and Trade (MoET) has high priorities to regulate competition, to enforce registration of offshore and foreign companies, and to negotiate with the World Trade Organization (Ministry of Economy and Trade, 2014). The MoET adopted three major European Union (EU) programs: the SME Support Program, the Quality Control Program, and e-Commerce (Abi Habib, 2008). Also, several initiatives with the World Bank and the international Finance Corporation have been taken to facilitate doing business (Kemayel, 2015). In addition, the Ministry of Industry is another government body that is working on boosting conditions for entrepreneurial and industrial development (Abi Habib, 2008). It promotes cooperation between leading universities and the Association of Lebanese Industrialists to introduce SMEs support to its curriculum, such as in the Lebanese University, and to sponsor business incubators. Also, the Ministry of Finance (MoF) is searching for solutions to lessen barriers to registration and issues relating to stamp duties and tax inspectors (Kemayel, 2015).

On December 6, 2005, the Lebanese government launched an integrated SME Support Program sponsored by the Minister of Economy and Trade, the Ministry of Finance, and the EU Ambassador. This program aims to provide the framework for related policies and aid the Lebanese government in developing a total approach to

support local SMEs, which will definitely encourage the country's development (Kemayel, 2015).

Lebanese laws require companies to register at foundation at the commercial register, with the NSSF (the government's insurance scheme), and with tax authorities at the Ministry of Finance. However, Lebanon has a large informal sector with widespread unregistered enterprises and employment. More than half of the SMEs are not commercially registered, and only 20% participate in the NSSF (Ministry of Economy and Trade, 2005).

Since most registered SMEs are family businesses their names and brands refer to the name of the family or the founder. Next, I will explore the literature on the reasons why Lebanese choose to operate legally, illegally, or as a franchise.

Reasons for Operating Legally, Illegally, or as a Franchise

Reasons for Operating Legally

Family businesses established in Lebanon had the ability to settle despite the environmental challenges of the country due to the instability of the economy and the political unstable situation (Williams, 1992). Lebanese entrepreneurs tend to establish a family business due to its simple establishment. However, it turns to be complicated with the development of the business and market, especially when it comes to the transfer of the ownership from generation to generation (IDAL, 2004). The business is not considered a game that can be restarted easily after losing it; therefore, the entrepreneur who wants to establish a business under the form *family business* must take into consideration the risks of conflicts that may be faced in the future. This means that the owner must be careful in managing his business, especially in the relation between the business and the family members (Vukotich, 2011). Moreover,

the owner determines the mission, vision, and goals of the company, the structure of the business, and the business procedures.

Jammal (2014) points that Lebanese SME are created to create a “financial safety net” for families (para. 1). A recent report from the Ministry of Economy and Trade (2014) indicates that Lebanese businesspeople are highly entrepreneurial, and open businesses to “exploit business opportunities” (p. 27).

There are many documentations needed to open a legal business in Lebanon. The first ones are to obtain a work permit, and a Commercial Registry. “All companies established in Lebanon must abide by the Lebanese commercial code and regulations, and are required to retain the services of a lawyer” (U.S. Department of State, 2013). In addition, establishing a new business requires a number of documentation enabling to start operating. Those documents required for the business to operate must be processed in several ministries, including the Ministry of Trade and Commerce, Ministry of Finance, and the Ministry related to the type of the business. It is also required to open a bank account according to the nature of the company, such as sole proprietorship, partnership, L.L.C under constitution, or corporation (Abdul Karim, 2003).

When family firms operate legally, the business can form a reputable and steady collaboration with customers, banks, and suppliers and could avoid going through undesirable penalties. Some business details should be taken into account, such as type of ownership, participating members, fees and costs.

The owners need also to prepare, either by themselves or delegating the managers, the company’s By-Laws and sign it before a Public Notary (U.S. Department of State, 2013). Moreover, managers, legal advisors, and internal auditors should be selected and officially appointed to their responsibilities. At this point, the

managers are responsible to sign fulfilled commercial circulars. The founders shall present to the chosen bank the company's By-Laws, minutes of held meetings, and legal identification of each partner, and open a bank account to deposit the required capital amount mentioning the division of shares and acquiring the proof that help to go further with the remaining requirements (IDAL, 2004).

On a later stage, at the Trade Register, partners themselves or delegating the registered lawyer have to submit the previous listed documents together with a Deed of property-rent already settled and recorded at the appropriate Municipality. The court of commerce will then appoint a complementary external auditor for the company. The founders are then requested to pay an amount of LBP 750,000 along with 0.3% of the paid-up capital at the Ministry of Finance; this capital will be then released after submitting certified copies of the documents mentioned earlier and company's By-Laws (U.S. Department of State, 2013). Additional documents would be demanded to be submitted at the Municipalities Union. These are related to the type of business, and are necessary to get construction permits, then the company will attain the Registration Receipt that in turn accredit the business to operate legally.

Trademark number and name are necessity for every registered business. These are obtained from the Ministry of Economy as the exclusive legal characteristic for the business, and play the essential role in protecting every registered company from imitation and duplication. (Khoury, 2013). Moreover, further petition may be required from the Ministry that is responsible for the sector in order to properly establish certain businesses in Lebanon (Ministry of Economy and Trade, 2014). Lastly, all prepared and officially obtained documents, should be submitted to the Commercial Register with a deadline of 30 days from the date of formation for final registration under one of the following allowed forms—such as Joint liability

company, Limited partnership, Undeclared Partnership, and Limited Liability Company (Kemayel, 2015).

Family businesses provide a lot of benefits for the economy in which they operate due to their long-term stability. In general, owners of family businesses believe on specific values that lead to an honest commitment to quality, and being responsible for the surrounding environment (Sreih & Pistrui, 2013). In Lebanon, the majority of SMEs are family business or even family companies. Some of them became popular names, such as Al Rifai, Al Halabi, Maatouk, Abi Khalil, and many others that are operating in different industries.

Reasons for Operating Illegally

Lebanon suffers from a high number of illegal small businesses that try to avoid paying taxes to the government. This is allowed because the government does not do any effort to make all establishments legal (Marseglia, 2004).

In addition, Lebanese entrepreneurs open illegal businesses because they seek to reduce costs, be profitable, and succeed in the country. As a result, some SMEs are registered and pay a lot of taxes, while other firms in the same industries are competing with lower costs and prices.

Reasons for Operating as a Franchise

Due to globalization, big companies have penetrated Lebanon to take advantages of the resources and increasing market. There are many businesses in the Lebanese market under the form of franchise, like KFC, McDonalds, and a big number of known brands (Porter, 2007). Franchise is an alternative to building chain stores to distribute goods that avoids the investments and liability of a chain. To avoid

liabilities and big investments establishing chain stores, franchise can be the alternative choice. (Porter, 2007).

The presence of franchises results in tougher competition, with advantages and disadvantages to other competitors. The franchisor's success depends on the success of the franchisees. However, small family businesses are obliged to survive in their local area, by competing with big international chains (franchises). The competition between the local and the international companies creates good opportunities for every entrepreneur to enhance and improve their skills. This means that due to competition, a lot of local small businesses have succeeded, to the point of exporting or starting to export their products to other countries (Dubrin, 2013).

Owners' Behavior Regarding Finances and Human Resources

Finances

Regarding finances, Naimy (2004) reported that 80% of SMEs self-financed their operations, 17.5% used loans from banks, and 2.5% used equity. More recently, an NGO reported that 72% of SMEs self-financed their operations, 14.4% used loans from friends, and 7.5% used loans from banks (International Rescue Committee, 2016). Table 1 shows the comparison between these two reports.

Table 1

SMEs Financing Strategies

	Self-financing	Loans from banks	Loans from friends	Equity
Naimy (2004)	80%	17.5%		2.5%
International Rescue Committee (2016)	72%	7.5%	14.4%	

Human Resources

In general, family SMEs recruit based on their network or community connections. However, preferring and depending on network connections within the organization more than know-how and experience conduce to unfair conditions for some employees, thus leading to a low level of motivation and competency (Soini & Veseli, 2011).

Some researchers claim that it is better to consider casual approach in small enterprises. Hill and Stewart (1999) stated that by simplifying the operation in small businesses the ability to deal with the higher levels of environmental uncertainty becomes attainable. On the other hand, others have different perspective, they believe that considering informal and flexible approach in small organizations leads to low performance in human resources management. For instance, Hendry et al. (1991) argue that excess workshop and training for employees of small businesses can be superfluous when they exceed the necessary needs of firm operations and that it can be only provided when the company is making high profits. Besides, Golhar and Deshpande (1997) claim that underestimating the importance of human resources management by small business entrepreneurs has a direct effect on firm-size differences in HRM practices.

Aside from being described as informal, small and medium enterprises are known to be less specialized than greater organizations. Specialists are more likely to be found in big corporates than in SMEs where employees have to perform a wide variety of tasks. Heneman and Berkley (1999) prove this point of view within the human resources management function, when a random sample of 117 companies with less than 100 employees, shows that only 15 have an HRM department. In addition to those studies, several small pilot and case studies have been completed by

analyst, increasing the evidence that HRM routine can be much more sophisticated than figured in a regular SME. For example, Deshpande and Golhar (1994) conclude that HRM procedures within many small manufacturing businesses are sophisticated as much as in bigger enterprises. Similarly, Hornsby and Kuratko (1990) see that when companies of all sizes recruit depending on informal methods or selection techniques, mainly employee referrals and the interview, HRM procedures in companies seem to be more sophisticated than assumed. Counting on a particular set of samples, Hill and Stewart (1999) also explain the variation in level of sophistication of HRM procedures by all of small enterprises.

Relationships Between Owners and Employees

Since the majority of Lebanese SMEs are family business, owners aim to behave as dictators, due to their full authority and control of the major procedures and daily decisions (Eikebrokk and Olsen, 2005). They tend to believe they are the sole source of information and knowledge for the organization. If Managers does not belong to the family, they struggle to please the founders more than creating new strategies that enhance the fulfillment of the business (Kemayel, 2015). This lack of confidence in the employees' involvement leads to unpleasant relationships and low commitment of the workforce (Mallett & Wapshott, 2014).

Organizations should have the awareness to recruit the right person for the right position, taking into consideration the needed skills and experience for the job (Hill & Stewart, 1999). In addition, the performance of the employees within the organization is crucial if aligned with the executives' vision of achieving efficiently the objectives of the organization, and aiming to be market leaders.

Profitability Impact: Illegal and Franchise

Legal SMEs are facing a strong competition from both the illegal and franchise firms causing a negative impact on their profitability. Diewert (1992) defined productivity as the ratio of outputs generated by specific inputs; thus, growth in productivity is the rise in output given a certain level of inputs.

Illegal firms adversely impact the profitability of SMEs. Since illegal businesses invest in inputs that exclude the expenses of registration fees and taxes, they offer their products at a lower price than legal firms (Ministry of Economy and Trade, 2014). As a result, legal businesses are obliged to lower their prices, thus decreasing their profitability.

On the other hand, franchises also negatively impact SMEs' profitability. Franchises are able to set high prices based on their brand name and global reputation, which local firms lack (Khoury, 2013). Furthermore, franchises normally enjoy higher demand from customers because of the brand name, resulting in lower demand and profitability for local firms (Porter, 2007).

Future of SMEs in Lebanon

Economists project both a bright and a dark future for SMEs in Lebanon. On the bright side, despite the barriers faced by family business in Lebanon, there are a number of family businesses established that maintain success and growth (Kemayel, 2015). The fast development of the global concept of business, which includes technology and transportation, leads to daily opportunities for change and growth for family businesses. Similarly, the International Rescue Committee (2016) forecasts that “despite [the] impact of crisis and competition, many businesses see themselves as stable with few dramatic shifts upcoming” (p. 12).

The future of SME was set by a strategy that indicates the roadmap to 2020 by the Ministry of Economy and Trade (Abi Habib, 2016). This strategy set a long term planning that motivate and support the small business to become large companies. “The Ministry of Economy and Trade will continue working with the key stakeholders from the public and private sectors to ensure the proper and effective implementation of this strategy, in order to empower and develop this important SME economic sector and promote economic growth, job creation and sustainable development” (Ministry of Economy and Trade, 2014).

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

In this chapter I will describe the research design chosen, the data collection methods, the population and sample, the data analysis method, and some ethical considerations.

Research Design

The research questions in this study call for a mixed methods design. A mixed methods design supplements the weaknesses and strengths of each type of data with the strengths and weaknesses of the other (Punch & Oancea, 2014). For instance, a mixed method design will incorporate the survey data strengths “of conceptualizing variables... [and] tracing trends and relationships” (Punch & Oancea, 2014, p. 339), with the qualitative data strength of “sensitivity to meaning and to context, local groundedness, the in-depth study of smaller samples” (p. 339). Another reason to choose the mixed method design is to investigate the nuances faced by different types of SMSs (legal, illegal, or franchised firms) from both management and employees’ perspective. Thus, while the survey questionnaire will analyze the frequency of a certain number of factors affecting small businesses, the interviews of managers will enrich those factors as well as probe for additional insights.

Data Collection Methods

In this study, the data collection methods are interviews and a survey. Six interviews will be conducted with six managers working in three different types of businesses: legal, illegal, and franchises. Two interviews will be conducted with

managers working at *Jaune* and *Kababji*, representing legal family business. Two interviews will be conducted with owners of two illegal (or not registered) businesses, a restaurant and a clothing firm. And two interviews will be conducted with managers working at *H&M* and *Burger King*, representing franchise SME.

Interviewees will be asked to sign an Informed Consent Form that protects their participation and take into account ethical considerations. The interviews will be conducted following an Interview Guide (see Appendix A).

On the other hand, a questionnaire was developed (see Appendix B) and was distributed over a sample of 80 respondents selected by convenient sampling from 8 different businesses in industries such as restaurant, printing, trading, and retail stores. The questionnaire aimed to answer the five research questions based on the opinion of owners, managers, and employees, providing a wide range of analysis about the challenges that face entrepreneurs to establish a business in Lebanon. Table 2 indicates the relationship between each research question, and data sources.

Data Analysis Methods

The data analysis for the quantitative data was descriptive statistics.

The data analysis method for the qualitative data consisted in subdividing the transcripts of the interviews into codes—labels that describe pieces of data (Creswell, 2008). Codes were then grouped into themes to develop higher order categories (Yin, 2011). To help in the analysis and since in qualitative data analysis writing coexist with analysis, explanatory research memos were written to capture insights and connections between different portions of the data (Silverman & Marvasti, 2008).

Ethical Considerations

To protect participants, the researcher respected their privacy. While collecting the data about the challenges to manage a business in a low market share country, efforts were made to avoid harming any of the participants. The researcher protected the privacy and confidentiality of interviewees by not reporting any information that would reveal their identities. Similarly, survey participants were not required to provide their identities and all analysis is reported in aggregate form.

CHAPTER 4

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In this chapter, I will report the analysis of the data collected. The chapter is structured in the five research questions, preceded by a description of the research participants. The five research questions are: reasons for operating legally, illegally, or as franchise; owners' behavior regarding finances and human resources; relationships between owners and employees; profitability impact: illegal and franchise; and future of SMEs in Lebanon.

Population and Sample

The population of this study is all SMEs in Lebanon. The sample in this study is formed by 14 SMEs, chosen by convenient sampling. Individuals from six SMEs were interviewed, and 80 individuals from the other 8 SMEs participated in the survey.

These 14 SMEs were represented by 86 participants. 70% of them were male and 30% of them were female (Table 3). This fact may indicate that males are more involved than females in establishing businesses in Lebanon. According to Blominvest bank, women make up half of the Lebanese population, yet only 21% are part of the labor force compared to men's 66% (Blominvest Bank, 2012).

Table 2

Triangulation Matrix of the Relationship of Research Questions with Data Sources

RQ	Survey Question	Interview Question		
		Not-Registered	Legal	Franchise
1	3, 4, 5, 6	1, 3	1	
2	7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 17, 19, 21, 22, 23, 24	2, 4	4	2, 4
3	15, 16			
4	25, 26		2, 3	1
5	18, 20, 27	5	5	3, 5

Table 3

Sample participants' gender

	Male		Female		Total Participants
	Participants	%	Participants	%	
Interviews	4	66.6%	2	33.4%	6
Survey	56	70%	24	30%	80
Total	60	69.7%	26	30.3%	86

The age of the participants of the survey is analyzed for additional insight. Four age groups describe the participants' ages. The majority of respondents belong to the age group between 30 and 34 years, with 30%. It may indicate that the young generation is interested in establishing businesses, regardless of whether they are family members. An additional 40% falls in the adjacent groups; 20% belongs to the age group between 25 and 29 years, and 20% belongs to the age group 35 to 39 years old. The remaining 30% is split between the other three groups; 10% belong to the

age group between 20 and 24 years, who may be young employees or one of the young family members; 10% belongs to the age group between 40 and 45 years; and 10% belongs to the age group over 45 years. In general, there is diversity in the age groups in SMSs in Lebanon (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Age groups.

Reasons for Operating Illegally, Legally or as a Franchise

Both the survey and the interviews were used in answering the first research question. Regarding the survey, questions three, four, five, and six were analyzed. As for the interviews, question one and three from the not-registered SME, and question one from the legal SME were analyzed.

Survey Analysis

In question three of the survey, participants were asked about the type of the business they are working in. The answers indicate that 50% are not registered, 25% are legal and registered based on the Lebanese government requirements, and 25% are franchises.

In question four of the survey, the respondents were asked about the reason for not registering their business. The majority, 56.25%, explain their decision to remain unregistered as result of belonging to a low market share country. 25% of them point to the high registration fees, 12.5% notes that the business is not registered in order to avoid taxes, and 6.25% to their inability to afford the money (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Reason for not registering.

In the fifth question in the survey, the respondents were asked about the factors that encourage them to select the legal business. They refer their selection for different reasons. 41.25% said that the reason for the registration of the business was the desire to expand through establishing different branches in different locations and even outside the country. 28.75% refer their legal registration of their business to the desire to protect their brand name. 18.75% of them said that they respect the Lebanese law, and 11.25% indicated other factors, such as including the competitive advantages, and the added value of the legal documentation (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Reasons for selecting a legal form of business.

In the sixth question of the survey, the representatives of SMEs were asked about the factors that encourage them to work with a franchise. For this question, 60% notes as reason the good reputation, and 40% refer the selection to the high demand of the franchise. Interestingly, no one refers to avoiding the major business establishment decisions.

Interview Analysis

Not registered. The first question asked to the two interviewees who were selected from illegal businesses addressed the reasons for not registering the business in Lebanon. One reason they noted was the small Lebanese market. Moreover, they are operating in a location targeting a small segment and not all the Lebanese market. Thus, the participants said that the market they are targeting is too small. In addition, they mentioned that since they finance the business from their own savings, they are not able to afford the registration fees.

In the third question, they were asked about the advantages and disadvantages of not registering their firm. The interviewees noted that performing a business

without registering has both advantages and disadvantages. The advantage is that it decreases expenses, such as the fees of documentation and taxes. On the other hand, the disadvantage is that the illegal business is not able to offer formal invoices due to the requirements of a legal documentation. Moreover, the illegal business is not able to expand and grow through branches. Add to that, the illegal business fails to establish a strong team due to the absence of a human resource department.

Legal. The first question of the interview with representatives from two legal SMEs inquired about the obstacles that the managers of legal businesses face. The participants from the two selected companies, *Jaune* and *Kababji*, noted somehow the same answers. Both interviewees said that it is not easy to register the business due to the requirements of different documents that the business should prepare. They mentioned the long time required to prepare the documents that need to be signed by different offices, starting from the Municipality where the business will be operating, followed by the signature of different ministries that the business type belongs to, in addition to the signature of the Chamber of Commerce, Industry, and Agriculture in Beirut. Moreover, the two interviewees have noted that there are many regulations involved in the registration that limit the requirements for the business, such as the number of staff, and the number of transportation they can use. The participants said that the registration of the business in Lebanon requires a lawyer who normally asks for high fees to register the business.

In summary, the findings show that half of the Lebanese SMEs that participated in this study are operating illegally, 25% are operating legally, and 25% are working in franchised businesses. The main reasons for operating illegally—in order of importance—are: low market share (56.25%), to avoid paying high registration fees that will increase the start-up cost budget (25%), to avoid taxes paid

to the government in order to decrease the costs of production (12.5%), and due to the inability to afford money for registration since they are operating a very small business that target small area which means that it cannot cover the registration fees (6.25%).

The reasons that motivate businesses to operate legally are: to expand the business into branches (41.25%), to protect the brand name from being imitated by competitors (28.75%), to respect the Lebanese law that regulate the businesses in the market (18.75%), and to gain the competitive advantages and the added value of the legal documentation that permit them to innovate and take actions that cannot be feasible without registration (11.25%).

Lastly, the reasons for operating franchise are the good reputation, and the higher demand.

Owner's Behavior Regarding Financing and Human Resources Functions

In order to answer the second research question—owner's behavior regarding financing and human resources functions—both the survey and the interviews were used. Regarding the survey, fourteen questions were analyzed. As for the interviews, two questions from the illegal and franchise interviews, and one question from the legal interview were analyzed.

Survey Analysis

The questions and analysis is divided in four areas: structure, finance, HR, and management.

Structure. In question 7 of the survey the participants were asked about the organizational form of their business. 31.25% are Limited Liability companies, 23.75% partnerships, 18.75% sole proprietorships—founded by one entrepreneur—

and 11.25% of the respondents noted that the type of the business is corporation—which was started as a family business as well. In addition, 15% indicated their business is second-hand, purchased from the founder (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Organizational form.

In question 8 of the survey, the participants were asked about the way in which the business was established. 37.5% were established by the owner/s who is/are entrepreneur/s. Besides, there is another 37.5% of family businesses that were transferred from a previous generation by inheritance. The other 25% indicated that the way of establishing the business was through purchasing an existing business.

And in question 9 of the survey the participants were asked about their personal role in the business. The four major categories that people are related to the organization are ownership, management, family members, and employees. The findings show that 38.75% belongs to the family, 37.5 are owners of the businesses, 15% are employees, while 8.75% are managers (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Role in the firm.

Finance. In question 10 in the survey, the participants were asked about the number of family members who are investors in the business. Usually, SMEs are financed by the investments of a number of the family business. The findings of this survey show that in 32.5% of the SMEs surveyed only one family member invests in the business, in 32.5% there are two family members investing in the business, in 18.75% four or more family members invest, in 10% there are 3 family members investing, and 6.25% were not family businesses (see Figure 6).

Figure 6. Number of family members who are investors.

In question 13 in the survey, the participants were asked about the way of financing the business. SMEs in Lebanon are financed in several ways. The findings show that 37.5% are financed through Kafalat loans, 25% are financed by the owner/s, 25% are financed through family member investments, 6.25% are financed through personal loans, and 6.25% are financed from other ways, such as selling land (see Figure 7).

Figure 7. Financing sources.

Human resources. In question 11 in the survey, the participants were asked about the number of family members who are full-time employees. In general, SMEs that are family businesses give the priority for employment to family members. This study found that 41.25% of SMEs employ 2 family members full-time, 21.25% employ one family member, 7.5% employ 3 family members, and 8.75% employ 4 or more family members full-time. On the other hand, the findings show that 21.25% does not include any family member as a full-time employee (see Figure 8).

Figure 8. Family members who are full-time employees.

In question 12 in the survey, participants were asked about the number of family members who are part-time employees. Interestingly, the findings show that 32.5% does not include any of the family members for part-time employees. 32.5% of SMEs employ one family member as a part-time employee, 27.5% notes that there are 2 family members, 3.75% notes that there are 3 family members that work part-time in the business, and 3.75% said that there are 4 or more family members who work part-time (see Figure 9).

Figure 9. Family members who are part-time employees

In question 21 in the survey, participants were asked their level of agreement with the idea that conducting training for the transition from generation to generation decreases the risk of failure. 75% of participants agreed (48.75%) or strongly agreed (26.25%). 5% neither agreed nor disagreed, and 20% disagreed (11.25%) or strongly disagreed (8.75%) that conducting training decreases the problems of transition. It seems that there is general agreement that businesses that ensure a successful transfer from one generation to the next, though not a simple process, achieve long-term success (see Figure 10).

Figure 10. Conducting training decrease problems of transition.

Management. In question 14 of the survey participants were asked about the type of individual managing the business. SMEs in Lebanon are managed through several types of individuals. The findings show that 60% of SMEs are managed by either the owner (37.5%) or a family member (22.5%). On the other hand, 40% of SMEs are managed by a hired manager (28.75%) or by an external consultant (11.25%) (see Figure 11).

Figure 11. Type of manager.

In question 17 in the survey participants were asked about their level of agreement with the idea that the establishment of clear boundaries that isolate the business interest from the family interest result in effective management. The majority (76.25%) either strongly agree (51.25%) or agree (25%) that separating the interests of the company from the interests of the family is a way to secure effective management. On the other hand, only 12.5% either disagree (10%) or strongly disagree (2.5%). 11.25% neither agree nor disagree.

In question 19 in the survey, the participants were asked about their level of agreement with the idea that having regular meetings to define, implement and control goals and objectives contributes to effective management. The findings show that 70% either strongly agree (40%) or agree (30%). On the other hand, 22.5% either disagree (12.5 %) or strongly disagree (10%). And 7.5% neither agree nor disagree that effective management involves regular meetings (see Figure 12).

Figure 12. Effective management involves meetings.

In question 22 of the survey, the participants were asked about whether management conflicts affect negatively the growth of local businesses. While 60% agree (30% strongly agree and 30% agree), 30% disagree (12.5% disagree and 17.5% strongly disagree) that there is a direct relationship between management conflicts and bad performance of the organizations. 10% neither agree nor disagree (see Figure 13).

Figure 13. Management conflict affect the growth of local business.

In question 23 in the survey, the participants were asked about their agreement with the idea that lack of management diversity affects the growth of the business. The majority (68.75%) believes that lack of diversity affects negatively the growth of the business (40% strongly agree and 28.75% agree). While 8.75% is neutral, 22.5% does not believe that the lack of the management diversity affects the growth of the business (12.5% disagree and 10% strongly disagree) (see Figure 14).

Figure 14. Lack of management diversity affects the growth of local business.

Finally, question 24 of the survey asked participants about their level of agreement with the notion that the SMEs' inability to fire family members affects the growth of the business. Since in the local businesses family members are not always hired based on qualifications, when they cause problems in the business, it is very difficult to fire them. The findings show that 91.25% of participants agree (61.25% strongly agree, and 30% agree), 1.25% neither agree nor disagree, and 7.5% disagree (1.25% disagree, and 6.25% strongly disagree) that family business' inability to fire family members affects the growth of the business.

Interview Analysis

Human resources. *Not- Registered.* Regarding the challenges that the illegal businesses face in managing their human resource functions, in question 2 the interviewees said that the illegal business face a lot of difficulties in establishing an organizational structure. Therefore, the owner of the business is obliged to fulfill different positions in the business. Moreover, the illegal business in Lebanon is not able to have any department; especially the human resource department, that regulate the issues related to human capital. Thus, the illegal business does not provide any commitments for employment. The illegal business, according to the two interviewees, is not able to do any of the human resource functions, which means that they do not provide any training for the employees. Moreover, they do not make any action that motivates and improve the performance of the employees. Thus, the illegal businesses face significant challenges in the human resource functions.

Participants were also asked (in the fourth question) to describe the market (Lebanon, MENA, and world) taking into consideration the human resources. The two interviewees said that illegal business is not a safe and protected business, since their market is very small, inside the small Lebanese market. They both agreed that they do not have the chance to expand to MENA region or to operate globally.

Usually, the illegal businesses operate in very small market, such as operating a mini market, a clothes store, or a small restaurant in a small street or village. The offered product or service of an illegal business is not able to satisfy high demand due to many lacking capabilities, especially qualified human resources.

Legal. Similarly, participants representing the two legal SMEs were asked to describe the market (Lebanon, MENA, and world) taking into consideration the human resources (fourth question). Legal businesses operating in the small Lebanese

market tend to expand in small branches within the country, but find it very difficult to expand abroad. The two interviewees described the Lebanese market as a low market share country that includes high competition preventing the legal business from being able to operate globally.

The two interviewees talked about their human capital since they consider them the main factor that affects their success. They noted that the low salaries in Lebanon influence the performance and the productivity of Lebanese employees. As result of high turnover, the interviewees said that they are facing problems in preparing, training and developing their human capital, without being able to satisfy their financial needs.

The two interviewees described the Lebanese and the MENA market as a consuming market that encourages and persuades investors to invest. However, the high cost of production and the high uncontrolled competition prevent legal businesses from growing to reach the global market.

Franchise. The participants from franchise companies were also asked to describe the market share (Lebanon, MENA, and world) taking into consideration their HR (question 4). Franchises are usually widespread internationally, proving that it can succeed in different markets and cultures. Similarly, the Lebanese market have proven to be successful for both H&M and Burger king. Therefore, both interviewees said that they are expanding in the market to be able to be accessible for the majority of their customers in Lebanon. The two interviewees noted that the main success of their business is the highly trained employees and committed human resources who are able to increase customer's satisfaction.

Management. *Franchise.* The participants from franchise companies were also asked about the challenges faced (question 2) in managing a franchise in

Lebanon. They mentioned the high start-up costs, certain rules to be followed, and the long-time commitment needed. The two interviewees said that the franchisee have to pay a big amount of money at the beginning of the purchase of the franchise, in addition to the big amount of start-up cost in order to implement the decoration agreed in the contract. Moreover, the franchisee should respect the rules which prevent the owner from making any personal management strategy. The franchisee faces the challenge of being committed to do everything set in the franchise agreement, making it difficult sometimes to fit in the culture of the new country.

In summary, owners' behavior regarding finance and HR differ based on the type of business (see Table 4). The owners of legal SMEs, establish the structure of their business in the form of sole proprietorship, partnership, and Limited Liabilities Company. The owners of legal SMEs finance their business through their personal money, family investment, or through applying for an SME's loan. Regarding the human resource, the owners of the legal SMEs offer low salaries and no training and motivation which increase the employee's turnover. As for the management, the owners of legal SMEs manage their business directly or hire a family member or external managers.

The illegal business owners behave in a way that differs from the legal owners since they manage their business by themselves, and they have difficulties in establishing an organizational structure which means that they do not have department and commitments to their employees. They finance their illegal business through personal investment or loan, family investment, and through selling a property such as land.

The behavior of owners of franchised business is more organized. First, the majority of its structure is corporation, financed by a loan or an investment from a

local company. The HR department focuses on training, motivating, and developing the employees. The board of director manages the franchised business based on the regulation of the mother company.

Table 4

Owners' behavior regarding finances and human resources

	Legal	Illegal	Franchise
Structure	- Sole proprietorship - Partnership - Limited liabilities company	- Difficulties in establishing an organizational structure	- Corporation
Financing	- Personal investment - Family Investment - SMEs loans (Kafalat)	- Personal investment or loan - Selling land/ family investment	- Loans - Company's investment in franchising
Human resources	- Low salaries - High turnover - Problems in preparing, training and developing human capital	- No HR department - No commitments for employment	- Highly trained employees and committed human resources who are able to increase customer's satisfaction
Management	- Owner management - Hired managers - Family member managers	- Owner management	- Board of directors

Relationship Between Owners and Employees

The third research question, relationships between owners and employees, is analyzed through question 16 from the survey.

Survey Analysis

In question 16 in the survey, the participants were asked about the ways in which owners deal with employees. The findings show that 58.75% of respondents agree that owners act as dictators in the way they deal with employees, while 18.75%

note that owners behave as leaders. 12.5% refers to owners as delegating and empowering employees, while 10% mentions other ways of dealing with employees, such as motivating, giving warnings, and terminating (see Figure 15).

Figure 15. Relationships between owners and employees.

Based on the results above, one can understand that the relationships between owners and employees are almost based on dictatorship, where few of the SMEs are adopting the leadership, delegation, and empowerment relationships.

Profitability Impact: Illegal and Franchise

The fourth research question revolved around the impact of illegal and franchise companies on the profitability of legal SMEs. Again, there are 3 survey questions and 3 interview questions that help to shed light on this issue.

Survey Analysis

In question 15 of the survey participants were asked about the main problems they face in the family business that prevent achieving growth and maintain success.

The data shows that 38.75% of the respondents indicate high competition from illegal and franchise business as the main problem faced. 22.5% of SMEs face family member conflicts, 18.75% struggle with ineffective decision processes, 10% points to the problem of the employee turnover, while 10% notes the political and economic instability that affects negatively on the business (see Figure 16).

Figure 16. Problems faced by SMEs.

In question 25 of the survey, the participants were asked about their level of agreement with the statement, “legal business are paying high costs which decrease their revenue compared to illegal business”. Fees of documentation and legal requirements increase the costs of the legal business, which decrease its ability to compete with illegal businesses. The findings show that 78.75% of respondents agree (38.75% strongly agree and 40% agree), 10% neither agree nor disagree, and 11.25% disagree (2.5% disagree, and 8.75% strongly disagree).

Question 26 of the survey dealt with the efforts made by legal businesses to maintain a strong brand that would enable them to compete with franchised businesses. The findings show that 50% of legal businesses agree (31.25% strongly

agree and 18.75% agree) that the legal businesses make a lot of effort, 11.25% is neutral, and 38.75% disagree (11.25% disagree, and 27.5% strongly disagree).

Probably the somewhat high level of disagreement is due to the fact that unlike them, franchised businesses have a global good reputation and global support that helps them in passing all the challenges that may be related to the market-share.

Interviews Analysis

Legal. The second question to legal SMEs inquired about the challenges faced by competing with illegal businesses. The two interviewees blamed the government for not making any effort to protect their businesses. The interviewees noted that the illegal businesses are operating in the same industries in a free way without being controlled by the government. They said that the illegal businesses are operating unfairly since they are not paying any registration fees, and also they are not paying any taxes. In addition, the illegal businesses are hiring employees, advertising for their businesses, and operating under a brand name and a logo without any effort from the government to regulate them. The two interviewees said that the challenge faced by the existence of illegal businesses is that they provide the same products at lower prices, since they do not calculate the registration fees and taxes in their pricing strategies.

On the other hand, interviewees from legal SMEs were asked about the challenges they are facing by competing with franchises companies (question 3). The two interviewees agreed that franchises are making the entry and the success of legal businesses very difficult, since franchised international brands are trusted more by customers. The interviewees noted they are both competing with franchised brand names to protect their brand image and customer loyalty and trust. They both agree that customers trust the brands that proved to expand internationally more than the

local brands even though customers are aware about the fake advertisements that franchises adopt.

Franchise. Representatives from the two franchises were asked about the profitability of their companies (in question 1). Both interviewees, from H&M and Burger King, noted franchises can achieve high profitability due to the strong brand name that is acquired globally. Franchised businesses are able to penetrate the market easily due to their popularity, and customers trust what was achieved in other countries. Besides, the franchised businesses select locations to operate that can target the highest number of customers possible. The two interviewees described the franchisee profitability as high.

They described the market as a high consuming one, compared to the small market share.

In summary, the findings show that the main problems faced by legal SMEs in Lebanon are the high competition by illegal and franchises, family members conflict, ineffective decision-making, employee turnover, and economic instability. Moreover, the legal businesses are paying high costs for registration compared to illegal, and making a lot of effort to compete against the strong reputation of franchised businesses.

Future of SMEs in Lebanon

The fifth research question, the future of SMEs in Lebanon, is answered through three questions from the survey, and four questions from the interviews.

Survey Analysis

In question 18 of the survey, the participants were asked if having a succession plan is an indicator of effective management. Family businesses that incorporate

succession plans are more likely to set strategies that decrease the problems and conflicts on the performance and the productivity of the business. The majority, 70% (58.75% strongly agree and 11.25% agree), agree that the formulation of a succession plan secures effective management. 10% neither agree nor disagree, and 20% disagree (11.25% disagree and 8.75% strongly disagree) (see Figure 17).

Figure 17. Succession plans and effective management.

In question 20 in the survey, the participants were asked if family members' conflicts may lead to the close of the business. Conflicts between owners affect negatively the performance of the business. The findings show that 80% agree (57.5% strongly agree and 22.5% agree), 8.75% neither agree nor disagree, and 11.25% disagree (8.75% disagree and 2.5% strongly disagree) that conflicts among family members who own a firm may result in the closure of the business.

In question 27 of the survey, the participants were asked if a long-term plan is key to the success of the business. Firms that do not have a long-term strategy that

includes a clear mission, vision, and strategic objectives, may find it hard to achieve sustainability and growth. The findings show that 70% agree (50% strongly agree and 20% agree), 7.5% neither agree nor disagree, and 22.5% disagree (12.5% disagree and 10% strongly disagree) that long-term plans are critical for the success of the business (see Figure 18).

Figure 18. Long-term plans lead to the success of the business.

Interviews Analysis

Illegal. The two interviewees who were selected to represent the segment of illegal businesses in Lebanon noted that the majority of the people who start a business without registration have as main goal to register it. The interviewees said that they recognize the importance of the registration of the business in order to expand the market share. They both agreed that the illegal business is always worried from being stopped by the government; therefore, they do not widen their operations.

This means that the preferred future of an illegal business is its transformation to a legal and registered business that is able to be protected and grow inside or outside the Lebanese market.

Legal. The future of legal SMEs in Lebanon is threatened by many factors. The interviewees agreed on the factors that affect the growth of their businesses. Starting from the seasonality of the demand in the Lebanese market, passing through the high political and economic instability, ending with the uncontrolled competition.

The interviewees referred to many examples about legal companies that were forced to close and be out of the market due to inability to cover the high costs of production, such as the closing of *Safir newspaper* after 42 years of operations.

From this point, the two interviewees describe the future of their business as unstable and unclear since they may be obliged to close if the demand and sale continue to decrease below the costs.

Franchise. According to the two interviewees, franchises have high chances of success because they are marketing proven products and managerial strategies. The advantages of the franchise are that the franchisee offer consumers high quality and consistency. Moreover, the franchisee gets the important support from the franchisor regarding the location selection, the design, and training of the staff. In addition to that, franchises get ongoing management support which increase the competitive advantages. The disadvantages of the franchises are that the franchisee is not independent since they are required to operate their businesses according to the procedures set in the franchise agreement. In addition, the franchisee not only pays franchise fees but should also pay ongoing advertising fees. The two interviewees mentioned that the future of their businesses in Lebanon will be successful, with

increased profitability due to their commitment, quality, and support from their franchisor resulting in gaining a higher market share.

In summary, the future of illegal businesses is stagnant and risky, the future of legal SMEs is unstable and unclear, and the future of franchises SMEs includes high chances of success through sustained competitive advantage. The preferred future for the illegal business is to transform it to legal through registering it. The interviewees of the illegal business mentioned that these businesses operate in small area which prevent them from establishing departments that organize the operations of the business, which means that they are not a safe business that can expand and achieve growth.

The future of the legal business in Lebanon is threatened by a lot of factors, such as the inability to generate profits in a low market to cover high expenses. The interviewees of the legal businesses note that the low wages in Lebanon affect employee performance and productivity. In addition, the low market share motivates legal businesses to expand through branches. The two interviewees blamed the government for not making any effort to protect their businesses against the existence of illegal businesses with lower prices for the same products. Moreover, the interviewees consider the strong brand loyalty from Lebanese customers toward franchises as a challenge for their businesses. The results of the survey show that the future of SMEs is threatened by family conflicts (80%), by lack of succession plans (70%), and by lack of long-term plans (70%).

The future of franchises in Lebanon is promising, with additional success due to the high quality, commitment, and to the support of international chains. The managers of the franchises interviewed (H&M and Burger King) forecast a bright

future, pointing also to franchises' high profitability, highly trained employees, and committed human resources.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this chapter I will summarize the conclusions, the implications, and the recommendations for future research.

Conclusion

In this section I will summarize brief answers to each of the five research questions.

The first research question inquired about the reasons to operate legally, illegally, and as franchise. My data shows that legal companies operate as such legal to leave the door open for growth and expansion, to protect their brand, to respect the law and to gain competitive advantage. Illegal companies choose to operate illegally because of their low market share, unwillingness to pay high registration fees, to avoid payment of taxes, and their inability to pay the registration fees. SMEs choose to operate as franchises to take advantage of their good reputation and high demand of their products and services.

The second research question revolved around the behavior of owners regarding finance and HR. While in legal companies HR departments exist but they are not developed, illegal companies are not able to have HR departments resulting in lack of training and motivation for employees. Franchise companies are in a better position because they have HR departments that train and motivate employees. Concerning owners' behavior on financing their business illegal businesses finance

their operations through personal investment or loan, family investment, and selling property such as land. Owners of legal SMEs finance their business with personal or family investment, or benefiting from low interest loans such as Kafalat. Franchises finance their operations from loans or investment from a parent company.

The third research question addressed the nature of their relationship between owners of SMEs and employees. The findings show that most of owners behave as dictators and few as leaders that delegate and empower their employees.

The fourth research question analyzed the impact of franchise and illegal companies on the profitability of legal SMEs. The profitability of legal SMEs is affected by the high competition from illegal companies and franchises. Regarding the illegal, in many industries, legal SMEs have higher costs resulting in lower profitability. Legal SMEs lose market share and profitability against franchises that enjoy higher levels of reputation and trust from customers.

The fifth research questions tried to predict the future of legal, illegal and franchise companies in Lebanon. Some of illegal businesses plan to register their companies to be able to grow and to avoid being in risk to be forced to close. The future of legal SMEs is unstable and unclear because of uncontrolled competition and the decreasing demand of the local brands. The future of franchises includes high chances of success and high market share are result of proven managerial strategies, high quality, and support from franchisor. The future of the three type of businesses is threatened by the unstable economic and political situation.

Implications

In this section I will discuss the theoretical, managerial, and governmental implications.

Theoretical Implications

In this section I will highlight points that my data supports and that challenges the literature review.

Supports. My data supports Eikebrokk and Olsen's (2005) statement that the relationships between owners and employees in Lebanon are based on the dictatorship style. My study also supports Khoury (2013) and the Ministry of Economy and Trade (2014) who argued that illegal businesses and franchises negatively influence SMEs' profitability. According to Marseglia (2004), the Lebanese government is not applying the law in making all the establishments' legal which is the main reason that the unregistered business dominates the market. The findings of my survey and the interview agree with Marseglia (2004).

The study found that some SMEs operate legally in order to protect the business and to be able to expand in branches and outside the country. This confirm several authors who note the steps and requirements to register a family business in Lebanon (Abdul Karim, 2003; IDAL, 2004; Jammal, 2014; Kemayel, 2015; U.S. Department of State, 2013; Ministry of Economy and Trade, 2014; Sreih & Pistru, 2013; Vukotich, 2011; Williams, 1992).

My findings show that the franchised business provides the owner with the advantages of strong global support, good reputation, and increased quality of services, as mentioned by Porter (2007).

The results show that the local respondents agree with the literature since they are not applying HRM in their small businesses in Lebanon. For instance, Hill and Stewart (1999) proposed that HR should be flexible in small business, Hendry et al. (1991) conclude that owners of small companies do not consider training as a

necessity, and Golhar and Deshpande (1997) consider that small business owners do not understand the importance of HRM on their performance.

Lastly, the participants confirmed the idea (Khoury, 2013; Ministry of Economy and Trade, 2014) that the franchised and illegal businesses affect the performance of the SMEs legal business negatively in a low market-share country, which lead to the closure of the majority of them.

Challenges. My study challenges that self-financing is the most used financing source (International Rescue Committee, 2016; Naimy, 2004), but that rather Kafalat loan is the most used financing source followed by personal saving, family investments or personal loans.

My study challenges the forecast of a stable future and prediction of success and growth for legal SMEs (International Rescue Committee, 2016; Kemayel, 2015). On the contrary, this study dark, unstable and unclear future for legal SMEs.

Lastly, my findings challenge the idea that owners create legal SMEs as safety net (Jammal, 2014) and to secure long term stability (Sreih & Pistrui, 2013). Rather, my respondents point to the need to expand and protect their brands.

Governmental Implications

I recommend Lebanese authorities who set regulations for establishing new businesses to develop policies that support and protect the legal businesses. Moreover, the government is recommended to be strict in helping illegal businesses to register. This will support the legal businesses in gaining profitability because there will be fair competition.

In addition, since there no adequate regulations to protect the national industry, I recommend the government to develop clear laws that protect local SMEs

from strong competition from international franchises, such as appropriate controls and regulations of franchise agreements.

Implications for SMEs

Legal SMEs' owners are recommended to establish a human resource department that organizes the human resources issues, such as training, motivation, and empowerments. This suggestion enhances and improves the performance and productivity of employees which may increase the satisfaction of the customers.

Legal SMEs are also recommended to hire managers who adopt the leadership relationship with the employees in order to be able to perform as a team.

Lebanese entrepreneurs are recommended to be trained on how to successfully plan, open, and operate an SME.

Illegal businesses are recommended to find ways to register and convert into legal business. This will help their business to grow, to be accepted by society and to help the national economy.

Several illegal businesses could unite their forces and form one stronger legal entity. Thus, they will behave with more confidence and be able to benefit from the opportunities and advantages of legal entities, such as loans, higher market share and stronger human resources.

Lastly, I recommend Lebanese entrepreneurs to enhance the local industries by investing in local businesses rather than international franchises. The benefits will be lower unemployment rate, specially among youth, increased gross domestic product, among others.

Recommendations for Further Research

I recommend further research to develop a detailed plan for the government to protect the national industry and combat illegality. I also recommend future studies to confirm the findings of this study with a larger sample size. I recommend scholars to design and propose ways to help Lebanese owners to nurture their relationships with their employees, considering the particular cultural aspects. Lastly, I recommend scholars to do case studies on examples of both successful and unsuccessful SME's in Lebanon, that can help Lebanese entrepreneurs to imitate successful practices and avoid failure.

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APPENDIX A
INTERVIEW GUIDE

A. Interviews with legal small family business

1. What obstacles you faced in the registration of your business?
2. What challenges do you face by competing with illegal firms?
3. What challenges do you face by competing with franchises? Profitability may not be the only challenge?
4. Describe your market (Lebanon, MENA, and world) taking into consideration your human resources.
5. How do you describe the future of your business?

B. Interviews with not registered business

1. Why is your business not registered?
2. What are the challenges that you face in managing your human resource functions?
3. What are the advantages and disadvantages of not registering your firm business?
4. Describe your market (Lebanon, MENA, and world) taking into consideration your human resources.
5. How do you describe the future of your business?

C. Interviews with franchisee

1. How do you describe your franchisee profitability?
2. What challenges do you face in managing a franchise in Lebanon?
3. What are the advantages and disadvantages of operating in a small market such as Lebanon?
4. Describe your market (Lebanon, MENA, and world) taking into consideration your human resources.
5. How do you describe the future of your business?

APPENDIX B
SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

This questionnaire is a set of ended closed questions about the challenges that face entrepreneur who establish family business in Lebanon. All information that respondents provide us will remain strictly confidential, it will be used for no other purpose than for this study, and the answer will be reported in aggregate.

1- Gender:

- Male Female

2- Age:

- 20-24 25-29 30-34 35-39 40-45 Over 45

3- Type of company

- Not Registered Legal Franchise

4- If not registered, select the most factor that encourage you to select this type:

- High registration fees Avoid taxes low market share other, please specify...

5- If legal, select the most factor that encourage you to select this type:

- Respect the Lebanese law protect the brand name expanding other, please specify...

6- If Franchise, select the most factor that encourage you to select this type:

- Good reputation high demand other, please specify...

7- Type of your business

- Sole proprietorship Corporation Limited liability company
- Partnership Other.....
- 8- The way of the establishment of the business
- Own establishment inherit purchase
- 9- Occupation in the firm:
- Owner Manager Family member Employee
- 10- Number of family members that are investors (If you are not the owner, you can skip)
- 0 1 2 3 4+
- 11- Number of family members that are full-time employees
- 0 1 2 3 4+
- 12- Number of family members that are part-time employees
- 0 1 2 3 4+
- 13- Ways of financing of the business (If you are not the owner, you can skip)
- Own finance Family members investments Kafalat Loan
- Personal Loan Other, please specify.....
- 14- Who manage the business?
- Owner manager Family member Manager Hired Manager
- External Management Consultant
- 15- What are the main problems that the firm is facing?
- Family members conflict Ineffective decision Employees turnover
- High competition from illegal businesses and franchises other.....

16- The owner of the small family business deal with employees based on:
 Dictatorship Leadership Delegation and empowerment other, please specify

17- Establishing clear boundaries that isolate the business interest from the family interest refers to the effective management.

Strongly Agree Agree Neither Agree nor Disagree Disagree Strongly Disagree

18- Formulate a succession plan for the family business refers to the effective management.

Strongly Agree Agree Neither Agree nor Disagree Disagree Strongly Disagree

19- Effective management involves having regular meetings to define, implement and control goals and objectives.

Strongly Agree Agree Neither Agree nor Disagree Disagree Strongly Disagree

20- Family members' conflicts may lead to the close of the business.

Strongly Agree Agree Neither Agree nor Disagree Disagree Strongly Disagree

21- Conducting training for the transition from generation to the next decrease the risk of failure in the shed of competition.

Strongly Agree Agree Neither Agree nor Disagree Disagree Strongly Disagree

22- Internal problems between the management affect the growth of the local business.

Strongly Agree Agree Neither Agree nor Disagree Disagree
Strongly Disagree

23- Lack of diversity in the managerial structure affects the growth of the local business.

Strongly Agree Agree Neither Agree nor Disagree Disagree
Strongly Disagree

24- Inability to fire family members who are not working affects the growth of the local business.

Strongly Agree Agree Neither Agree nor Disagree Disagree
Strongly Disagree

25- Legal business are paying high costs which decrease their revenue compared to illegal business

Strongly Agree Agree Neither Agree nor Disagree Disagree
Strongly Disagree

26- Legal businesses are making a lot of efforts to build strong brand compared to franchise

Strongly Agree Agree Neither Agree nor Disagree Disagree
Strongly Disagree

27- Long term plan is the key of success of the business.

Strongly Agree Agree Neither Agree nor Disagree Disagree
Strongly Disagree

Thank you...